

Collective and Stochastic Motion in the Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation Part 3 Propagators

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In a previous note (1) Part 2, we compared two approaches to solving the Schrodinger equation: $i\partial/\partial t (\text{partial}) W(x,t) = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W + .5kxx W + f(t)x W$ ((1)), with both utilizing the idea of a transformation, namely $y=x-b(t)$. The first approach involved unitary transformations, while the second changing variables and searching for a product wavefunction W_0W_1 such that W_0 satisfies the oscillator equation without $f(t)x$ (but with a $c(t)W$ term easily handled by a time phase) and W_1 satisfies a Schrodinger like equation containing $f(t)y$ and a coupling term $-1/2m dW_0/dy dW_1/dy$ such that $i d/dt \text{partial} W_1$ cancels this term.

In this note, we consider a third approach, that of propagators outlined in (2). This method may be used to find the propagator of ((1)). Interestingly, following (2), one may postulate a propagator solution of the form $G_0(x,t)\exp[i (a(t)x + b(t)x_1 + g(t))]$ where $G_0(x,x_1,t)$ is the oscillator propagator (without $xf(t)$). Thus, one does not ever use the transformation $y=x-b(t)$ unlike the previous two approaches. This different approach, however, requires explicit knowledge of $G_0(x,x_1,t)$, the oscillator propagator. There are no “cancellations”.

Given that the two previous approaches involve a solution containing $W_n(y)$, where W_n is the time-independent oscillator solution in the variable $y=x-b(t)$, one might expect that a propagator for ((1)) should use a $G_0(y,t)$ and not $G_0(x,t)$. We show one may obtain the same results, by considering the use of a transformation y together with a propagator. Using y involves solving one differential equation as opposed to three for the non- y method.

In addition, we consider applying the approach of (2) to the calculation of $W(x,t)$. We find that $\exp(ia(t)x + ig(t))$ must be modified to $\exp(ia(t)x + B(t)x + ig(t))$ which may then be used to find the ground state solution of the oscillator plus $xf(t)$ Hamiltonian utilizing the explicit form of $W_0(x,t)$ the ground state. We argue that the transformation approach seems to be more convenient for higher energy levels

Propagators

Propagators $K(x,t, x_1,t_1)$ may be used to “propagate” a wavefunction i.e.

$$W(x,t) = \text{Integral } dx_1 dt_1 K(x,t,x_1,t_1) W(x_1,t_1) \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{Sometimes } t_1=0)$$

The propagator may be computed using Feynman’s path integral approach, but is also linked to a Green’s function through:

$$G(x,t, x_1,t_1) = \text{Heaviside Step function} * K(x,t,x_1,t_1) \quad ((3))$$

$K(x,t,x_1,t_1)$ is thus a solution of the time dependent Schrodinger equation and:

$$[i\partial/\partial t \text{partial} - H] G(x,t,x_1,t_1) = \delta(x-x_1)\delta(t-t_1) \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{a usual Green’s function requirement})$$

For example, for the free particle propagator ($H = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$) from (3):

$$K = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^{1/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk \exp(ik(x-x_1)) \exp(-ikkt/2m) = \sqrt{m/(2\pi\hbar t)} \exp[i\frac{m(x-x_1)^2}{2t}] \quad ((4))$$

The $\exp(i g(x,t))$ form may be shown to be a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. To recover the more familiar $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ solution consider ((2))

$$W(x,t) = \int dx_1 \int dk \exp(ik(x-x_1)) \exp(ipx) \exp(-ikkt/2m) \text{ and interchange } dx_1 \text{ and } dk.$$

Then: $\int dx_1 \exp(-ikx_1) \exp(ipx_1) = 2\pi\hbar \delta(p-k)$ and one has:

$\int dk \exp(ikx) \delta(p-k) \frac{1}{2\pi\hbar} \exp(ikkt/2m) = \exp(ipx) \exp(i Et)$ where $E = p^2/2m$ or the free particle wavefunction.

In (3), the propagator for the quantum oscillator is given as:

$$K(x, x_1, t) = \sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{2\pi\hbar i \sin\omega t}} \exp(i \{ \frac{m\omega}{2} (x-x_1)^2 \cos\omega t - 2xx_1 \} / \sin\omega t) \quad ((5))$$

Quantum Oscillator with an Extra $x f(t)$ Potential

We wish to consider here the problem:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 W + x f(t) W \quad ((6))$$

i.e. a quantum oscillator with an extra $x f(t)$ potential. In (1), we considered two methods involving the transformation $y = x - b(t)/m$. In this note, we follow the method of (2) which argues one may seek a solution to ((6)) of the form:

$$K(x, x_1, t) = K_0(x, x_1, t) \exp[i (a(t)x + B(t)x_1 + g(t))] \quad ((7)) \text{ where } K_0(x, x_1, t) \text{ is the oscillator propagator which must be known explicitly i.e. ((5)).}$$

No notion of transformation is needed. Treating $K_0(x, x_1, t) \exp[i (a(t)x + B(t)x_1 + g(t))]$ as a product solution, substituting into ((6)) and comparing x , x_1 and pure time terms yields three differential equations which may be solved for $a(t)$, $B(t)$ and $g(t)$. The key point, unlike the case of the transformation methods, is that one must know the explicit form of $K_0(x, x_1, t)$ as it is used to calculate $d/dx K_0$. (In the transformation approach, one changes variables to $y = x - b(t)$ and postulates a solution of the form $\exp(i y \frac{db}{dt}) W(y, t)$. One then obtains two differential equations from the single Schrodinger equation. The first applies to $W(y, t)$ as a solution of the oscillator time-independent Schrodinger equation with an extra $c(t)W(y, t)$ term (easily handled by a pure time phase). The second gives a differential equation linking $b(t)$ and $f(t)$).

Inserting $K(x, x_1, t)$ into ((6)) yields:

$$-K_0 \left\{ \frac{da}{dt} x + x_1 \frac{dB}{dt} + \frac{dg}{dt} \right\} = f(t) x K_0 + \frac{1}{2m} K_0 a - \frac{1}{m} \frac{dK_0}{dx} ia \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Using ((5)): } \frac{dK_0}{dx} = K_0 i \left(\frac{1}{\sin wt} \right) \{ m w \cos wt x - x_1 \} \left(-\frac{1}{m} \right) a(t)$$

One may compare terms of x , x_1 and pure time to obtain:

$$((9a)) \quad -\frac{da}{dt} = f(t) + \left(\frac{1}{\sin wt} \right) \cos(wt) w a(t)$$

$$((9b)) \quad -\frac{dB}{dt} = a(t) \frac{1}{\sin wt} \left(\frac{1}{m} \right)$$

$$((9c)) \quad -\frac{dg}{dt} = \frac{1}{2m} a(t)a(t)$$

The objective is to solve the interlinked equations ((9)).

$$((9a)) \quad \frac{d}{dt} [\sin wt a] = w \cos wt a + \frac{da}{dt} \sin wt \text{ so } a(t) \sin wt = -\int (0,t) dt_1 f(t_1) \sin wt_1$$

$$((9b)) \quad B(t) = \int (0,t) dt_1 a(t_1) / \sin wt_1 \text{ with } a(t) \text{ given above.}$$

$$((9c)) \quad g(t) = \frac{1}{2m} \int (0,t) a(t_1)a(t_1)$$

The propagator solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation usually differs from other solutions. For example, as seen above $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is the usual solution of a free particle Hamiltonian, but K from ((4)) is also a solution. It is interesting to compare the solution of ((6)) given in (1) using transformation methods. Two transformation methods were considered in (1), each yielding the same pure time dependence. The solution is:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(iEnt) W_n(y) \exp(i y \frac{db}{dt}) \exp(i \int c(t_1) dt_1) \quad ((10))$$

Where $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{db}{dt} = f(t)$, $y = x - b(t)/m$, E_n and W_n are oscillator energy and wavefunction and: $c(t) = f(t)b(t)/m - \frac{1}{2m}(\frac{db}{dt})(\frac{db}{dt}) + \frac{1}{2}k b(t)b(t)/m + \frac{d}{dt}(b/m \frac{db}{dt})$

Thus, the pure time-dependent phase is:

$$\exp(i b/m \frac{db}{dt}) \exp(i \int (0,t) \{ f(t_1)b(t_1)/m - \frac{1}{2m}(\frac{db}{dt})(\frac{db}{dt}) + \frac{1}{2}k b(t_1)b(t_1)/m + \frac{d}{dt}(b/m \frac{db}{dt}) \} dt_1) \quad ((11))$$

where $\frac{db}{dt} = m \int (0,t) f(t_1) dt_1$

One may see that in the solution of ((10)), different pure time phases appear (i.e. ((11))) than in $\exp(i dg/dt)$. Furthermore, ((11)) makes use of the integral: $\int (0,t) f(t_1) dt_1$ while $a(t)$ uses $\int (0,t) f(t_1) \sin wt_1 dt_1$ i.e. its Fourier transform with the frequency w of the oscillator if the integration bounds are chosen in a certain way. We investigate this further in later sections to show an actual equivalence.

Reconciling $y=x-b(t)$ with $K_0(x,x_1,t)\exp[i (a(t)x + b(t)x_1 + g(t))]$

In the two transformation procedures (which yield the same wavefunction), $W_n(y)$ is the oscillator n eigenfunction and $y=x-b(t)/m$. The oscillator solution is in the variable y , not x . This begs the question: Why does the propagator approach use $K_0(x,x_1,t)$ i.e. the variable x ? One might expect to have $K_0(y,x_1,t)$ if the two approaches are compatible and if there is a "physical" transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ in the system.

To consider this, one may write $K_0(y,x_1,t)$. The Hamiltonian only acts on x , so we leave x_1 unchanged.

To examine the transformation case, we utilize the oscillator ground state wavefunction $\exp(-Ayy)$ with $y=x-b(t)/m$ as an example and work in x and t :

$$W(x,t) = \exp(-iE_0t) \exp(i \int c(t_1)dt_1) \exp[i (x-b/m)db/dt] \exp[-A(x-b/m)(x-b/m)]$$

By inserting into the Schrodinger equation ((6)), one sees it is indeed a solution with:

$xm \frac{d}{dt} \frac{db}{dt} = xf + kb(t)x$ which defines $b(t)$. $c(t)$ represents all pure time terms which may be handled with a phase.

It seems one may write a propagator using $y=x-b(t)/m$ with $b(t)$ chosen so there is a fictitious potential which cancels $xf(t)$. In other words, the transformation approach should be applicable because one has a Schrodinger equation with an extra potential linear in x i.e. $f(t)x$. In particular, given that $K(x,x_1,t)$ is an exact solution of the Schrodinger equation ((6)) as is $W(x,t)$, the exact transformation arguments for $y=x-b(t)/m$ should apply to $K(x,x_1,t)$ as well. Thus, one may try:

$$K(x,x_1,t) = K_a(y,x_1,t) \exp(iy \frac{db}{dt}) \exp(i \int_{(0,t)} c(t_1)dt_1) \quad ((12))$$

The only difference is that for the wavefunction of (1), we use $W_a(y,t) = \exp(-iEt)W_a(y)$ whereas here, one leaves $K(y,x_1,t)$. The goal is to eliminate the extra potential $xf(t)$ and have $K_a(y,x_1,t)$ represent an oscillator propagator in the variable $y=x-b(t)/m$. Thus, one has:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{db}{dt} = f(t) + 2kb(t)/m \quad ((13)) \text{ just as in } ((1)).$$

The oscillator propagator $K_a(y,x_1,t)$ may be written as:

$$K_a(x-b/m,x_1,t) = K_a(x-b/m,x_1,t) \left[\exp\left\{-\frac{m\omega \cos \omega t}{2 \sin \omega t} \left[(x + \frac{b}{m}) - 2x_1 \right] - \frac{1}{\sin \omega t} (x-b/m)x_1 \right\} \right] \quad ((14))$$

We do not transform x_1 to $y_1 = x_1 - b(t)/m$, because the Hamiltonian ((6)) only operates on x (not x_1). Considering coefficients of the x term in the argument of the exponential yields from ((12)) and ((14))

$$db/dt - m\omega \cos \omega t / \sin \omega t = b/m \quad \text{which should equal } a(t) \quad ((15))$$

Using ((13)) and multiplying by $\sin \omega t$ yields:

$$d/dt (a(t) \sin \omega t) = \sin \omega t d/dt db/dt - \sin \omega t kb/m \quad ((16))$$

Integrating the first term on the RHS of ((15)) by parts twice ((16)) becomes:

$$a(t) \sin \omega t = \sin \omega t db/dt - \omega b \cos \omega t + \int \omega \sin \omega t b(t) dt - \int \omega \sin \omega t b(t) dt$$

$$\text{Or } a(t) = db/dt - \omega b(t) \cos \omega t / \sin \omega t \quad ((17))$$

Thus, ((15)) = ((17)) and one may transform $y = x - b(t)/m$ instead of using the approach of (2) i.e. $K(x, x_1, t) = K_0(x, x_1, t) \exp[ia(t)x + iB(t)x + ig(t)]$ to obtain the same result.

Applying the Propagator Approach to the Full Wavefunction

The propagator approach for the Schrodinger equation ((6)) involves postulating:

$$K(x, x_1, t) = K_0(x, x_1, t) \exp[ia(t)x + iB(t)x + ig(t)] \quad \text{where } K_0(x, x_1, t) \text{ is the propagator without the } x f(t) \text{ potential piece.}$$

It seems the above assumption is made explicitly for an $x f(t)$ type of potential. Nevertheless, one may suggest a similar method for the wavefunction for the same Schrodinger equation ((6)) i.e. $W(x, t) = W_0(x, t) \exp[ia(t)x + iB(t)x + ig(t)]$. ((18)) where $W_0 = \exp(-iEt) \exp(-Axx)$.

This approach, however, does not work. Consider $W_0 =$ the ground state wavefunction. If ((18)) is inserted into the Schrodinger equation and one tries to solve for $a(t)$ and $g(t)$, a term from $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W$ namely $-1/m i a(t) d/dx \exp(-Axx)$ results. This term is imaginary while all other terms are real.

The approach, however, may be modified to:

$$W(x, t) = W_0(x, t) \exp[ia(t)x + B(t)x + ig(t)] \quad ((19))$$

Then:

$$i(\dot{a} + \dot{B}) = f(t) - \frac{1}{m} (ia + B) (-2A) \quad ((20))$$

Comparing real and imaginary parts leads to: $-\dot{a} = f + B2A/m$ and $\dot{B} = 2Aa/m$ ((21)) ((20)) only holds for the ground state wavefunction, but one may see that $a(t)$ is proportional to \dot{B} . This is analogous to $\exp(i(x-b/m)\dot{B})$ and $\dot{B} = f(t)m$ in (1). Thus, for the ground state, it is simple to use a modified product wavefunction without any notion of a transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ to find the ground state wavefunction with the extra $xf(t)$ potential.

For higher energy levels, it seems it is more convenient to utilize $y=x-b(t)/m$ in order to eliminate $W_n(y)$. There is only one propagator for the oscillator and it is of a relatively simple form so $\exp(ia(t)x + iB(t)y + ig(t)) K_{osc}(x,x_1,t)$ works for all cases, but one is left with an integral $W_n(x,t) = \int dx_1 K(x,x_1,t) W_n(x_1,0)$ for each wavefunction. The transformation using y even applied to the propagator shows general properties of this transformation for all resulting wavefunctions and so one may use a consistent $y=x-b(t)/m$ for all cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine a method displayed in (2) for calculating the propagator of a quantum oscillator with an extra $f(t)x$ potential. (In (2), a different Hamiltonian is studied, but the method is the same.) The idea is that $K(x,x_1,t) = K_0(x,x_1,t) \exp(ia(t)x + B(t)x_1 + ig(t))$ where K_0 is the propagator of the Hamiltonian without the extra $xf(t)$. A key idea of the approach is that one must know the explicit form of $K(x,x_1,t)$ (because $d/dx K_0$ is calculated) and then obtain three differential equations for $a(t)$, $B(t)$ and $g(t)$ which are interrelated.

In (1), we consider two approaches to the same problem based on the transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$. We use the form $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) \exp(iy \dot{B}) W_n(y) \exp(i \int_0^t c(t_1) dt_1)$ and find that $W_n(y)$ satisfies an harmonic oscillator time independent equation in y with an extra pure time potential $c(t)$ if one allows for a cancellation of the terms $i dW_n/dy \dot{B} (1/m)$ from $i \dot{B}$ and $-1/m dW_n/dy d/dy \exp(iy \dot{B})$. In this way, no explicit knowledge of the form of $W_n(y)$ is needed for the cancellation.

We apply the transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ instead of the approach of (2) and show it yields the same result for the propagator of ((6)), as it should because the propagator is a solution of the time dependent Schrodinger equation and should follow the approach applied to $W(x,t)$. Furthermore only one differential equation needs to be solved.

We also find that the approach of (2) may be applied using the ground state $W_0(x)$ of an oscillator multiplied by $\exp(ia(t)x + B(t)x + ig(t)) W_0(x,t)$. We find the method is not convenient for higher order energy levels i.e. $W_n(x)$. Thus, we conclude that using a transformation $y=x-b(t)/m$ for an extra $xf(t)$ potential seems to make sense and may highlight some physical aspects of the problem .

References

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